

Quantity take-off and cost estimating with OpenBIM models: process automation for buildings

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Abstract

Quantity take-off and cost estimation is an important step in the lifecycle of a building since it establish a budget by measuring, quantifying, and estimating the elements needed for a construction project. Traditionally, this process was generated through the interpretation of 2D drawings by quantity surveyors, which often lead to challenges due to missing information. However, this process improved by the introduction of Building Information Modelling (BIM) by improving accuracy and collaboration between the different stakeholders. A BIM-based quantity take-off automates the measuring process by extracting the geometrical and alphanumeric information from all the elements of the 3D model.

Even through a BIM-based quantity take-off process some challenges still persist mainly because of inconsistency in the modelling process and data silos between the stakeholders. The following study aims to solve these issues by establishing an accurate and efficient quantity take-off and cost estimation procedure through three main steps: first, the generation of modelling rules and establishment of level of information need; second, generate a simplified and standardized process through a WBS structure (provided by CYPE, the company involved in this study); and third, following an OpenBIM-based approach which relies on the IFC

schema. This aims to promote interoperability and assuring a more standardized, efficient, and accessible quantity take-off process.

The main goal this work consists of the proposal of a new workflow defined by a standardized modelling process, a verification of the geometrical and alphanumeric information and a cost estimate of all the elements required for a project. This process should be applied to several architectural instances to determine a proper modelling process for each of them, followed by the establishment of the level of information need to get the information requested to generate a final project budget.

This workflow shall be generated through the definition of a literature review of the quantity take-off and cost estimation process at the time and modelling trials of each studied architecture instance. Through them, the process was established for the mentioned architecture elements by testing its export through an IFC file and by assigning their cost in an open-based platform that allows the integration of a project by using a cloud service, letting all stakeholders to upload and be aware of others work.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/uhG2WIYuuTo>

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10034118